

Adapting policy to facilitate the market entry of Hybrid True Potato Seed varieties

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- › Hybrid potato breeding holds large promise in increasing the sustainability and productivity of potato production.
- › Hybrid potato breeding strategies can be very fast, and targeted to address multiple stresses, including drought and disease.
- › Hybrid breeding results in True Seed starting materials instead of conventional tubers, which are virtually clean of pests and diseases.
- › Farmers in the EU can benefit from this technology in the future, but currently commercialization is a huge barrier.
- › Alleviating these barriers requires the adaptation of variety registration, certification and protection policies.

Introduction

Potato is the world's third most important food crop, and its importance to global food supply is expected to increase. The potato's nutritional value is high compared to other staple foods. However, climate change, pests and disease are creating challenges in potato production (Haverkort and Struik, 2015). Late Blight is causing annual crop losses of 3.5 billion € per year (FAOSTAT, 2017).

To combat the effects of climate change on yield, robust varieties that can withstand multiple stresses, such as lack of water and reduced nutrient availability, are needed. Whilst making positive contributions to addressing these issues in potato production, to a certain degree, conventional potato breeding has made limited progress, compared to yield gains achieved in other field crops (Rijk et al., 2013). Recently, a new form of breeding has emerged that involves hybrid diploid breeding, which is showing to be an accelerator of potato breeding. Diploid refers to the presence of two complete sets of chromosomes in an organism's cells, with each parent contributing a chromosome to each pair. Conventionally bred potato cultivars used in the incumbent potato

production are tetraploid containing four sets of chromosomes. Hybrid breeding promises much greater success in unlocking the potato's huge genetic diversity, as well as enabling greater resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses in the field. This novel breeding not only greatly enhances the speed of product development but also provides huge logistical and phytosanitary advantages. The result of diploid hybrid breeding is a Hybrid True Potato Seed (HTPS) variety.

The development of new potato varieties by means of hybrid seeds is a new development and results in a new type of plant propagating material for the EU: Hybrid potato seeds of True Seed Varieties (HTPS-varieties). Two regulatory barriers need to be resolved in order to fully exploit the benefits of this new development: first, distinctiveness, uniformity and stability (DUS)-testing for variety registration and Plant Variety Rights applications and, second, marketing and certification.

Approach and results

Breeding approaches and results from the SolACE project

In many crops, such as maize and tomato, hybrid breeding has increased yields and resulted in disease resistant varieties. Now that hybrid breeding is also available in potato (Lindhout et al, 2011), we have assessed whether experimental hybrids are ready for commercial application in different EU countries. Multi-year field experiments in different locations showed that experimental HTPS varieties have the potential to perform similarly to conventional potatoes (Stockem et al., 2020), see Figure 1. HTPS also showed promising results under conditions where multiple stresses were present, a phenomenon which as a consequence of climate change is expected to occur more frequently.

In the SolACE project, experimental hybrids were tested with an aim to develop a hybrid breeding strategy for multiple stresses for potato. The introduction and improvement of disease resistance was proven to be much faster in the experimental hybrids than in conventional potato (Su et al., 2020).

We have shown that in two years, we can introduce durable resistance in potato hybrids through classic breeding techniques. The resistance can reduce the environmental impact of chemical control of Late Blight, responsible for 7% of the total use of chemicals (FAOSTAT, 2019). The potential of HTPS was shown in practice in the SolACE project. The results will be used to generate further potato hybrids that will perform even better.

Challenges in EU legislation for commercialisation of novel potato varieties

The next step is to realize this potential by releasing HTPS varieties to potato farmers. The development of HTPS varieties for commercialisation is well underway. Several HTPS varieties have been submitted for variety registration and protection in The Netherlands since 2019. To allow EU farmers and consumers to benefit from improved varieties, policies regarding variety registration, Plant Variety Rights and certification and marketing require adaptation.

For variety registration as well as for Plant Variety Rights applications a DUS-test is used, to assess the Distinctness, Uniformity and Stability of a new variety. The current Technical Questionnaire (TQ) for DUS-testing is based on clonal tuber-propagated potato varieties. This protocol cannot be applied in all detail for HTPS varieties, so adaptations are needed to the uniformity requirements, propagating materials and field testing protocols. This concerns DUS-testing for National/EU variety listing, as well as DUS-testing for applications to obtain National or EU Plant Variety Rights. Proper DUS testing is an important step towards the commercialization of potato varieties on a large scale in the EU. When a variety is registered, alignment with the current certification system is possible. This ensures a high-quality standard of starting material for the growers.

The transition from clonally propagated material to seeds is not unique to potatoes. For strawberry the adaptation of the certification system for seed-based varieties is in progress, and in shallots, both seed-based and clonally propagated varieties are registered, protected and marketed.

Once a variety is registered (Certification and Marketing of true seeds) seedlings and potato tubers from HTPS-varieties need regulation. Council Directive 2002/56/EC defines the quality requirements for plant propagating material of potatoes in the European Union. These requirements are based on vegetatively propagated clonal potato varieties (tubers). The scenario that the marketing of true potato seeds, potato seedlings and first-generation tubers produced from HTPS-varieties are used for further propagation is not currently regulated in the EU.

The EU Temporary Experiment (Commission Implementing Decision EU/2017/547), is intended to provide answers on how and under what conditions to allow for the certification and marketing of potato tubers from HTPS-varieties in the EU. The Temporary Experiment ends in 2023 and should result in an update of Council Directive 2002/56/EC in 2024.

Additionally, the present policy to ban all imports from HTPS from outside the EU hampers seed production outside the EU, potentially increasing seed costs and complicating global logistics.

Figure 1: Transplanted potato seedling in the field

Figure 2: Cleaned rue potato seeds in a bottle and harvested berries containing seeds

Figure 3: Freshly harvested tubers from diploid hybrids grown from seedlings

Source: Solynta

Policy recommendations

The following regulatory gaps have been identified:

- › Potato tubers derived from HTPS plants need to be classified according to the existing seed-tuber certification scheme.
- › Minimum quality requirements for germination, purity and health status of true potato seeds should be defined.
- › Provision of quality requirements and inspection guidelines of seedlings of HTPS varieties intended to be transplanted for the production of potato tubers.

To make sustainable cultivation of potato possible, the EU should consider regulations regarding DUS-testing for variety registration. Plant Variety Rights applications and certification and marketing also need to be adapted to avoid delay in access to improved potato varieties for European farmers and consumers.

Conclusion

In summary, a new method to develop hybrid potato varieties has been developed. In the SolACE project, its applicability for multi-stress tolerance was tested. This new method can be instrumental to address environmental, food quality and food security challenges. At present several HTPS varieties have been submitted for Registration and Variety Rights. To avoid delay in their introduction, variety registration, certification and protection policies need adaptation to accommodate Hybrid True Potato Seed varieties.

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